

Theorems on Common Fixed Points in Complete Rectangular S-Metric Spaces

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 08 November 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: A. S. Saluja</p>	<p>In this paper, some common fixed point theorems are established in rectangular S-metric spaces, an advanced generalization of S-metric spaces. New common fixed point theorems are developed that integrate and extend various well known results in fixed point theory. The findings are further supported by illustrative examples.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Rectangular metric spaces, S-metric spaces, Rectangular S-metric spaces.</p>	

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important topics in the development of non linear analysis is fixed point theory. Fixed point theory has also been successfully applied to a variety of other fields of research, including chemistry, biology, economics, computer science, engineering and a variety of others. The concept of metric spaces has been generalized in various ways. The ideas

of 2-metric spaces and D-metric spaces were introduced by Gahler [5] and Dhage [3], respectively. The theory was further extended by Mustafa and Sims [6] to G-metric spaces. Novel concepts of D^* and S-metric spaces has been introduced by Shaban Sedghi [9,10]. In this paper, we find some new results of rectangular S-metric spaces and prove common fixed point theorems on some spaces .

2 PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. [12] Let X be a non-empty set and $S: X^3 \rightarrow R^+$, a function that satisfies the following properties:

- i. $S(p, q, r) = 0$ if and only if $p=q=r$
- ii. $S(p, q, r) \leq S(p, p, a) + S(q, q, a) + S(r, r, a)$

for all $a, p, q, r \in X$ (rectangle in equality)

Definition 2.2. [1] Let X be a non empty set and $S: X^3 \rightarrow R^+$, a function satisfying the following properties:

- i. $S(p, q, r) = 0$ if and only if $p=q=r$
- ii. $S(p, q, r) \leq S(p, p, a) + S(q, q, a) + S(r, r, a)$

for all $p, q, r \in X$ and all distinct points $a \in X - \{p, q, r\}$. Then (X, S) is called a rectangular S- metric space .

Definition 2.3. [12] let (X, S) be an S-metric space and $A \subset X$

- i. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X converges to x if $S(x_n, x_n, x) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, that is for every $\epsilon > 0$ there exists $n_0 \in N$ such that $n \geq n_0, S(x_n, x_n, x) < \epsilon$. This case ,we denote by $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x$ and we say that x is the limit of $\{x_n\}$ in X .
- ii. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ is said to be Cauchy sequence if for each $\epsilon > 0$, there exists $n_0 \in N$ such that $S(x_n, x_n, x_m) < \epsilon$ for each $n, m \geq n_0$.
- iii. The S-metric space (X, S) is said to be complete if every Cauchy sequence is convergent

Definition 2.4. [2] let f and g be weakly compatible self -maps of a set X . If f and g have a unique point of coincidence $w = fx = gx$ then w is the unique common fixed point of f and g .

Lemma 2.5.[12] If (X, S) is an S-metric space, then we have $S(x, x, y) = S(y, y, x)$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Lemma 2.6.[12] let (X, S) be an S-metric space. If $\{x_n\}$ and $\{y_n\}$ are sequences in X converging to x and y respectively, that is, $x_n \rightarrow x$ and $y_n \rightarrow y$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $S(x_n, x_n, y_n) \rightarrow S(x, x, y)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Lemma 2.7.[12] let (X, S) be an S-metric space. If the sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X converges to x , then the limit x is unique .

Lemma 2.8.[12] let (X, S) be an S-metric space. If the sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X converges to x , then sequence $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence.

Example 2.9. let $X = N \cup \{0\}$ and define $S: X \times X \times X \rightarrow R^+ \cup \{0\}$ by

$$S(p, q, r) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } p = q = r \\ px + qy + rz & \text{if } p \neq q \neq r \end{cases}$$

Then (X, S) is a rectangular S- metric space.

3. MAIN RESULT

Theorem 3.1: let (X, S) be a complete rectangular S-metric space and let g and h be a self mapping on X . Assume that g and h satisfies the following condition :

$$S(gx, gx, gy) \leq k[S(gx, gx, hy) + S(gy, gy, hx)]$$

Where $0 \leq k < 0.1$, also,

- i. $g(X) \subseteq h(X)$
- ii. If $h(X)$ is complete
Then g and h have a unique coincidence point in X .

Proof: let x_0 be any point in X .

Since $gx_0 \subseteq g(X)$ and $g(X) \subseteq h(X)$

There exists a point x_1 in X such that $gx_0 = gx_1$. As $x_1 \in X$, it follows that $gx_1 \subseteq g(X)$.

Thus , we can select x_2 in X such that $gx_1 = hx_2$. Repeating this process iteratively we construct a sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X where $x_{n+1} \in X$, satisfies

$$Gx_n = hx_{n+1} \text{ for all } n.$$

Now , consider

$$\begin{aligned} S(hx_{n+1}, hx_{n+1}, hx_n) &= S(gx_n, gx_n, gx_{n-1}) \\ &\leq k[S(gx_n, gx_n, hx_{n-1}) + S(gx_{n-1}, gx_{n-1}, hx_n)] \\ &= k[S(hx_{n+1}, hx_{n+1}, hx_{n-1}) + S(hx_n, hx_n, hx_n)] \\ &\leq k[S(hx_{n+1}, hx_{n+1}, hx_n) + S(hx_{n+1}, hx_{n+1}, hx_n) + S(hx_{n-1}, hx_{n-1}, hx_n)] \\ &= k[2S(hx_{n+1}, hx_{n+1}, hx_n) + S(hx_{n-1}, hx_{n-1}, hx_n)] \\ &\Rightarrow (1 - 2k)S(hx_{n+1}, hx_{n+1}, hx_n) \leq kS(hx_{n-1}, hx_{n-1}, hx_n) \\ &\Rightarrow S(hx_{n+1}, hx_{n+1}, hx_n) \leq \frac{k}{1 - 2k} S(hx_{n-1}, hx_{n-1}, hx_n) \\ &= tS(hx_n, hx_n, hx_{n-1}) \\ &\text{where } t = \frac{k}{1 - 2k} \end{aligned}$$

$$S(hx_{n+1}, hx_{n+1}, hx_n) \leq t^n S(hx_1, hx_1, hx_0)$$

For $m, n \in N$ and some $N \in N$ with $m < n$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} S(hx_n, hx_n, hx_m) &\leq S(hx_n, hx_n, hx_{n-1}) + S(hx_n, hx_n, hx_{n-1}) + S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-1}) \\ &\leq t^{n-1} S(hx_1, hx_1, hx_0) + t^{n-1} S(hx_1, hx_1, hx_0) + S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-1}) \\ &= 2t^{n-1} S(hx_1, hx_1, hx_0) + S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-1}) \\ &\leq 2t^{n-1} z + [S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-2}) + S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-2}) + S(hx_{n-1}, hx_{n-1}, hx_{n-2})] \end{aligned}$$

Where $z = S(hx_1, hx_1, hx_0)$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq 2t^{n-1} z + [2S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-2}) + t^{n-2} S(hx_1, hx_1, hx_0)] \\ &= 2t^{n-1} z + t^{n-2} z + 2S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-2}) \\ &\leq 2t^{n-1} z + t^{n-2} z + 2[2S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-3}) + S(hx_{n-2}, hx_{n-2}, hx_{n-3})] \\ &\leq 2t^{n-1} z + t^{n-2} z + 4S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-3}) + 2t^{n-3} z \\ &\leq 2t^{n-1} z + t^{n-2} z + 2t^{n-3} z + 4[2S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-4}) + S(hx_{n-3}, hx_{n-3}, hx_{n-4})] \\ &\leq 2t^{n-1} z + t^{n-2} z + 2t^{n-3} z + 8S(hx_m, hx_m, hx_{n-4}) + 4t^{n-4} z \\ &= 2t^{n-1} z + t^{n-2} z + 2t^{n-3} z + 4t^{n-4} z + \dots \\ &= 2t^{n-1} z + t^{n-2} z \left(1 + \frac{2}{t} + \frac{4}{t^2} + \frac{8}{t^3} + \dots \right) \\ &= 2t^{n-1} z + t^{n-2} z \left(1 - \frac{2}{t} \right)^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Where $z = S(hx_1, hx_1, hx_0)$, as $n \rightarrow \infty$

And since $t < 1$ we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} S(hx_n, hx_n, hx_m) = 0$$

Since $\{hx_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in $h(X)$. Since $h(X)$ is complete , there exist q in $h(X)$ such that $hx_n \rightarrow q$, as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Consequently , we can find p in X such that $hp = q$.

$$\begin{aligned} S(gx_n, gx_n, gp) &\leq k[S(gx_n, gx_n, hp) + S(gp, gp, hx_n)] \\ &= k[S(hx_{n+1}, hx_{n+1}, hp) + S(gp, gp, hx_n)] \end{aligned}$$

$$= k[S(q, q, q) + S(gp, gp, q)]$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$S(q, q, gp) \leq kS(q, q, gp)$$

Since $S(q, q, q) = 0$ and $k < 1$, this is true if $S(q, q, gp)$

$$\Rightarrow gp = q$$

Therefore $gp = hp = q$

Hence q is the point of coincidence of g and h .

Now we show that g and h have a unique point of coincidence .

For this assume that there exists another point $u \in X$ such that $gu = hu = u$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} S(q, q, u) &= S(gp, gp, gu) \\ &\leq k[S(gp, gp, hu) + S(gu, gu, hp)] \\ &= k[S(q, q, u) + S(u, u, q)] \\ &\leq k[S(q, q, u) + S(q, q, u)] \\ &= 2kS(q, q, u) \end{aligned}$$

Since $k \in [0,0.1)$. It is true if $S(q, q, u) = 0$. So $q = u$.

Hence it is proved that g and h have a unique point of coincidence.

Since g and h are weakly compatible. So by proposition 1.4, g and h have a unique common fixed point in X .

4 CONCLUSION

- From this paper we conclude the establishment of common fixed point theorems.
- Generalization of S -metric spaces.
- Integration and extension of results.
- These conclusions of the paper in the context of fixed point theory in the rectangular S-metric spaces.

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